

**New records of two beetle species in Hungary
(Coleoptera: Silvanidae, Eucinetidae)**

Dezső SZALÓKI^{1*} & Béla TALLÓSI²

¹ H-1183 Budapest, Kálti Márk utca 16, Hungary. E-mail: dezsoszaloki@gmail.com

² H-5000 Szolnok, Csokonai utca 23, Hungary. E-mail: tallosibela@gmail.com

Abstract – The first records of two beetle (Coleoptera) species, *Airaphilus perangustus* Lindberg, 1943 (Silvanidae) and *Nycteus hopffgarteni* (Reitter, 1885) (Eucinetidae) from Hungary are reported.

Key words – faunistics, distribution, *Airaphilus perangustus*, *Nycteus hopffgarteni*

INTRODUCTION

In the frame of our ongoing faunistical survey which includes collecting in various parts of Hungary and revision of material from public and private collections, two species were found to be new to Hungary. Necessary translations and explanatory comments to label data are given in square brackets, while the number of examined specimens and their depositories in parentheses.

Abbreviations – CBT = collection of Béla Tallósi, Szolnok; CDS = collection of Dezső Szalóki, Budapest; CJS = collection of József Sár, Kővágótöttös; CZS = collection of Zsolt Sággy, Székesfehérvár; HNHM = Coleoptera Collection of the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest; JPM = collection of the Janus Pannonius Múzeum, Pécs.

* Corresponding author.

RESULTS

Family: Silvanidae

Airaphilus perangustus Lindberg, 1943

(Figs 1–2)

Material examined – Hungary: Hajdú-Bihar county, Hortobágyi N. P. [= Hortobágy National Park], Újszentmargita, Margitai erdő [= Margita forest], 13.VI.1974, No 38., leg. Z. Kaszab (1 specimen, HNHM); Zala county, Kis-Balaton, Fenékpusztá, Halász-rét [= Halász meadow], 15–22.VI.2000, pitfall trap, leg. Zs. Sággy (1 specimen, CZS); same locality and collecting method, 30.VI.–6.VII.2000, leg. A. Takács & Zs. Sággy (1 specimen, HNHM); same data but 27.VII.–2.VIII.2000 (1 specimen, HNHM); same locality and collecting method, 29.III.–4.IV.2001, leg. Zs. Sággy (1 specimen, CZS); same locality and collecting method, 5–12.VII.2001, leg. A. Takács & Zs. Sággy (1 specimen, HNHM); same locality and collecting method, 26.VII.–3.VIII.2001, leg. Zs. Sággy (1 specimen, CZS); same data but 26.IV.–8.V.2002 (1 specimen, CZS); same data but 24.VII.–1.VIII.2002 (2 specimens, CZS); same data but 20.VI.–20.VII.2005 (1 specimen, CZS); Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg county, Bököny, Közös legelő [= pasture], 5.I.2021, singled under *Verbascum* leaves, leg. N. Tóth (1 specimen, CDS); same locality, 22.I.2021, sieving, leg. N. Tóth (3 specimens, CDS); same locality and collecting method, 30.I.2021, leg. D. Szalóki (7 specimens, CDS, 3 specimens, HNHM, 1 specimen, CJS); same locality and collecting method, 21.II.2021, leg. N. Tóth (2 specimens, CDS); same locality and collecting method, 24.III.2021, leg. D. Szalóki (1 specimen, CDS); Hajdú-Bihar county, Hajdúhadház, liget [= park], 27.IV.2021, sieving, leg. D. Szalóki (1 specimen, CDS); Hajdú-Bihar county, Újszentmargita, Dögös-lapos, rét [= meadow], 15.VI.2021, D-vac, leg. É. Szita (2 specimens, CDS); Győr-Moson-Sopron county, Kapuvár, Oslí-Hány, 29.IV.–26.V.2022, pitfall trap, leg. P. Kovács & Cs. Szinetár (2 specimens, HNHM).

Remarks – Previously only one species of the genus *Airaphilus* Redtenbacher, 1858, namely *Airaphilus elongatus* (Gyllenhal, 1813), was known from Hungary. However, congeneric specimens were collected in 2021 around Bököny (Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg county, Northeastern Hungary), and were identified as *Airaphilus perangustus*. Following this discovery, the authors examined the *Airaphilus* specimens kept in the HNHM, and it turned out that most of the specimens previously determined as *Airaphilus elongatus* were misidentified, and belong to *Airaphilus perangustus*, including the voucher specimen from the Hortobágy National Park, on which the first report of the Hungarian occurrence of *Airaphilus elongatus* was based (ÁDÁM 1983).

Airaphilus perangustus represents a new species to Hungary; previously this species was known from Finland, Poland, and Switzerland (HALSTEAD *et al.* 2007). Similar revisions of materials identified as *Airaphilus elongatus* and deposited in other European collections may reveal further country records for *Airaphilus perangustus*.

Proposed Hungarian name: karcsú fogasnyakú-lapbogár.

Identification – *Airaphilus perangustus* can be distinguished from *Airaphilus elongatus* by the following diagnostic characters: pronotum is conspicuously longer than its width; lateral margins of elytra are parallel, and almost 4× as long as their width at the level of the shoulders; antennae and legs are brown, and are relatively shorter than in *Airaphilus elongatus*. However, in *Airaphilus elongatus* the pronotum is slightly longer than its width (in males) or as long as its width (in females); lateral margins of elytra are curved, and less than 3× as long as their width at the level of the shoulders; antennae and legs are black, and relatively longer than in *Airaphilus perangustus*. Both species are small, body length of *Airaphilus perangustus* is 2.6–3.3 mm, and that of *Airaphilus elongatus* is 2.6–3.3 mm.

1

2

Figs 1–2. *Airaphilus perangustus* Lindberg, 1943, 1 = adult specimen (photo by Imre Retezár), 2 = its habitat at Bököny, Hungary (photo by Dezső Szalóki)

Airaphilus elongatus (Gyllenhal, 1813)

Material examined – Hungary: Baranya county, Villányi-hegység [= Villány Mountains], Harsányi-hegy [= Harsányi Mountain], 15.V.1972, leg. S. Horvatovich (1 specimen, JPM); Somogy county, Barcsi-ösborókás [= Barcs Juniper Forest], 24.XI.1979, leg. S. Horvatovich & J. Sár (1 specimen, JPM); Somogy county, Darány, Nagy-berek, 6.IX.1996, leg. A. Podlussány (1 specimen, HNHM).

Remarks – As noted above, part of the previously published data on this species (HORVATOVICH 1980, 1981, MERKL 1998) actually refer to *Airaphilus perangustus*. However, the specimens listed above were correctly identified as *Airaphilus elongatus*, therefore there is no need to delete this species from the fauna of Hungary. Based on the data above, adults of *Airaphilus* species can mostly be found in late autumn or early spring, in drying meadows and marsh habitats.

Family: Eucinetidae

Nycteus hopffgarteni (Reitter, 1885)

(Figs 3–4)

Material examined – Hungary: Baranya county, Kovácsszénája, Tekerési-völgy [= Tekerési valley], Herman Ottó-tó [Herman Ottó lake], 46°10'42"/18°07'13", 175 m, 26–27.VI.2021, leg. B. Tallósi (1 specimen, CBT, 1 specimen, HNHM).

Remarks – Previously only one species of the family Eucinetidae, namely *Eucinetus haemorrhoidalis* (Germar, 1818), was known from Hungary (MERKL & VIG 2011); this species is considered to be widespread in the Pannonian biogeographical region.

Here we report another species of the family, *Nycteus hopffgarteni*, as new to Hungary; the voucher specimen belongs to the *Nycteus hopffgarteni hopffgarteni* subspecies of the species.

According to VÍT (2006), *Nycteus hopffgarteni* was known from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and Yugoslavia (Serbia, Montenegro). The Hungarian record in VÍT (2006) is erroneous, as it is most probably based on a record from Herkulesfürdő published by KUTHY (1897), now belonging to Romania (Herkulesfürdő = Băile Herculane in Caraș-Severin county, Romania). Therefore, the first Hungarian record of this species is the one reported here.

Nycteus hopffgarteni is usually found in undisturbed, old forests, and develops in dead wood interwoven with fungal threads.

Proposed Hungarian name: Hopffgarten-álmaróka.

Identification – *Nycteus hopffgarteni* can be readily distinguished from *Eucinetus haemorrhoidalis* by the following diagnostic characters: body is yellowish-red with yellow pilosity or blackish brown with light shoulders and apex; apices of hind tibiae possess two large spurs; elytra are evenly punctate; body length 3.2–4.1 mm. This species is relatively stockier than *Eucinetus haemorrhoidalis*. In *Eucinetus haemorrhoidalis* the body is brownish black, while apices of elytra, antennae and legs are red; apices of hind tibiae possess one large spur; elytra are covered with dense, thin, transverse, scratched wrinkles; body length 3–3.6 mm.

3

4

Figs 3–4. *Nycteus hopffgarteni* (Reitter, 1885), 3 = adult specimen (photo by Imre Retezár), 4 = its habitat at Kovácsszénája, Hungary (photo by Béla Tallósi)

*

Acknowledgements – The authors are grateful to Imre Retezár for the photos, to Norbert Tóth for collecting some of the above reported specimens of *Airaphilus perangustus*, and to the staff members of the museum collections (HNHM, JPM). The voucher specimens of *Nycteus hopffgarteni* were collected during field work organised by the Hungarian Biodiversity Research Society.

REFERENCES

- ÁDÁM L. 1983: The species of Hydroadephaga, Clambidae, Orthoperidae and Diversicornia (in part) of the Hortobágy. – In: MAHUNKA S. (ed.): *The Fauna of the Hortobágy National Park, II*. Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest, pp. 155–166.
- HALSTEAD D. G. H., LÖBL I. & JELÍNEK J. 2007: Family Silvanidae Kirby, 1837. – In: LÖBL I. & SMETANA A. (eds): *Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, Volume 4. Elateroidea, Derodontoidea, Bostrichoidea, Lymexyloidea, Cleroidea, Cucujoidea*. Apollo Books, Stenstrup, pp. 496–501.
- HORVATOVICH S. 1980: Hazánk faunájára új és ritka bogárfajok a Dél- és Nyugat-Dunántúlról II. (Coleoptera). (For the Hungarian Fauna New and Rare Beetle Species from South and West Transdanubia II., Coleoptera.) – *Janus Pannonius Múzeum Évkönyve* 24: 33–43.
- HORVATOVICH S. 1981: Hazánk faunájára új és ritka bogárfajok a Dél- és Nyugat-Dunántúlról III. (Coleoptera). (For the Hungarian Fauna New and Rare Beetle Species from South and West Transdanubia III., Coleoptera.) – *Janus Pannonius Múzeum Évkönyve* 25: 71–83.
- KUTHY D. 1897: Ordo Coleoptera. – In: *A Magyar Birodalom Állatvilága. Fauna Regni Hungariae. III*. Királyi Magyar Természettudományi Társulat, Budapest, 213 pp.
- MERKL O. 1998: Data to 46 beetle families (Coleoptera) from the Duna-Dráva National Park, South Hungary. – *Dunántúli Dolgozatok Természettudományi Sorozat* 9: 209–232.
- MERKL O. & VIG K. 2011: *Bogarak a pannon régióban*. [Beetles in the Pannonian Region.] – Vas Megyei Múzeumok Igazgatósága, Szombathely, 494 pp.
- VÍT S. 2006: Family Eucinetidae Lacordaire, 1857. – In: LÖBL I. & SMETANA A. (eds): *Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, Volume 3. Scarabaeoidea, Scirtoidea, Dascilloidea, Buprestoidea, Byrrhoidea*. Apollo Books, Stenstrup, pp. 314.